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State-of-the-Art of AI implementation in childhood cancer

OPBG

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Abstract

A review of data from a bibliometric analysis, an analysis of existing reviews and ongoing projects registered in published repositories, show that AI applications in pediatric oncology are mostly limited to classification of diagnostic images in brain tumors. Data from MRI are the most used for this purpose while other data sources are less frequent in AI applications. Only a small proportion of existing studies on AI in pediatric oncology has compared the accuracy of AI algorithms with a natural person. Many registries for pediatric oncology exist in Europe, representing potential data sources for the development of AI applications. Data included in these repositories, however, are not harmonized, although several initiative have been carried out in Europe to pool together different registries for developing AI applications. Data sharing from clinical repositories among research centers is rarely accomplished due to complexity in internal policies and a restrictive interpretation of GDPR. The development of AI applications poses several ethical issues, from transparency of the algorithms to cybersecurity risks, that deserve a multidisciplinary approach. These issues are reflected in the communication process with the patient and ultimately in the informed consent. Finally, the application of AI in telemedicine for pediatric cancer seems unexplored. These results suggest that a strong impulse to overcome barriers in data sharing for developing AI for pediatric oncology is needed, that the use of AI should be evaluated in the full spectrum of cancer diseases in children using

solutions at diagnostic, prognostic or therapeutic level, including telemedicine. Finally, since children with cancer represent a fragile population affected by rare diseases, tailored approaches to investigate the ethical implications of AI should be developed.

Keywords

Bibliometric analysis; Clinical registries; Data repositories; Ethics; Telemedicine; Data sharing

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R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
HSCT	Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplant
ML	Machine learning
BRAF	B-Raf Proto-Oncogene, Serine/threonine Kinase
EEG	Electroencephalogram
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
CT	Computer Tomography
US	Ultrasound
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
GvHD	Graft versus Host Disease
CNS	Central Nervous System
GDPR	General Data Protection regulation
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
ALL	Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia
PGHD	Patient Generated Health Data
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
EHR	Electronic Health Record
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
IT	Information Technology

1. Executive summary

The main objective of EU4CHILD is to draw the state of the art of AI applications in pediatric oncology through the integration of different data from multiple sources to inform the development of a roadmap for future actions in this field.

We performed a thorough analysis of the state of the art in AI applications in pediatric oncology integrating views on trends in scientific publications, evidence from existing studies and reviews from multiple sources. We also screened and reviewed the available sources of data potentially useful to train AI algorithms in pediatric oncology. In addition, we explored existing ethical challenges in this domain simulating clinical scenarios. We finally screened the existing literature about the existing initiatives that integrate telemedicine with AI for pediatric oncology.

The volume of scientific publications on AI and pediatric cancer has increased exponentially since 2016 even though most scientific papers in this field have been published in journals not specialized in oncology. Several international collaboration networks contributed to the development of scientific papers in the application of AI to pediatric oncology with strong links between Europe, the US and China. When looking at results from European authors, the UK and Germany ranked as the most productive countries in this field. The majority of the available scientific papers are focused on applications of AI in imaging of brain tumors, especially on classification and automatic segmentation. Only a few studies, however, have validated the AI application with a human decision/interpretation. When reviewing the existing literature reviews, data confirm that AI for pediatric oncology has been studied mainly in the field of imaging of brain tumors for diagnosis and segmentation, and for extraction of radiomic features. The most important impact from available AI applications in pediatric oncology regards time saving for performing image examinations, and reduction to radiation exposure. AI in imaging in this field may help with the classification of tumors in which invasive procedures represent a significant risk. Secondly, the available reviews confirm that AI applications are helpful in prognosis prediction with a decent level of accuracy. These findings are confirmed from a review of studies registered on clinicaltrials.gov in the last 5 years. Indeed, the vast majority of the studies found in this repository focused on AI applications on brain tumors and radiomics. In addition to these topics, the ongoing studies found on clinicaltrials.gov included projects searching for novel tumor biomarkers and for the classification of skin lesions through teledermoscopy. According to these results, there is room for expanding AI studies to other frequent pediatric tumors such as leukemias and lymphomas.

Several registries for pediatric cancer exist in Europe and are currently used for scientific purposes, representing a suitable data source for the development of AI applications. Most of the registries are general and focused on pediatric cancer, although there is no apparent standardization of database structures. Other databases used in pediatric oncology are about survivorship and genomics in pediatric cancer. Several collaborations have been established

among different registries, resulting in collaborative studies that suggest an existing effort to pursue data pooling. However, although some of the published papers have been developed through collaborations across different registries, it is likely that data linkage and pooling required data normalization, integration and curation. In addition to children's registries, data from children have been derived from adult registries. The use of data from all these repositories is subject to specific agreements with the database owners and accessibility is regulated by GDPR and specific country laws. Of note, some registries offer synthetic data that resemble statistical properties of real data for research purposes to third parties. Some published papers have used open data repositories that can be reused by other researchers. However, the number of observations in these datasets is generally limited. Other open platforms for genomic data, diagnostic images and other clinical information exist and are commonly used in research focusing on AI. However, these platforms offer limited information that is diverse and represents different populations, and sometimes the available information is not specific for children.

The several dimensions of ethics in artificial intelligence applied to pediatric oncology has yet to be addressed. Several scenarios in which these issues become evident will only be recognized as challenging when AI will be fully integrated into healthcare. However, two main issues should be addressed from the very beginning: first, accuracy of AI algorithms based on deep learning depends on the amount of data used for training. Although it is mandatory to apply all rules and strategies that are designed for preserving the privacy of individuals, it may seem unethical to create barriers to data sharing that may prevent or delay the development of beneficial AI interventions. Secondly, the opacity of AI algorithms may prevent the understanding of their mechanism and question their justification when a clinical decision should be taken. This observation has important implications for the communication process with the patient and the informed consent in clinical studies on AI interventions.

Finally, the increased popularity of telemedicine has the potential to offer immense opportunities if combined with AI applications, even though our review of the existing literature did not identify any relevant study in this field applied to pediatric oncology. The tools that can be obtained ranges from the integration of patient reported outcomes into the clinical history of the patients, to the analysis of voice, personal images, and information streams produced by wearable devices.

2. State of the art of AI implementation in pediatric cancer

With the launch of the European Commission's document *Europe's Beating Cancer Plan* as recently as last year (2021), pediatric cancer has come to the top of the policy agenda in Europe and the European Union institutions have been summoned up to “do more to protect our children from cancer”.

Amidst such strong policy commitment, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is expected to contribute to the modern approach to cancer care that the Plan is advocating for. High expectations for AI are explicit in both EU cancer policies and in the European digital strategy documents, with the *2021 Review of the Coordinated Plan on AI* signaling that AI will be instrumental in strengthening cancer care. The document states that the Commission will “continue to support the deployment of the infrastructure needed to link and explore European databases, for example of medical images, of different types of cancer, and leverage AI technologies to exploit high-quality cancer imaging repositories”.

Similar strong convictions and high expectations for the use of AI in pediatric cancer are being shared by many in the European pediatric haematology-oncology community. For example, the 2021-2026 Update of the European Society for Pediatric Oncology (SIOPE) Strategic Plan has identified Big Data and Artificial Intelligence as a key strategic objective:

“In the next decade, there will be vast opportunities to translate artificial intelligence (AI) and Big Data into clinical practice but there is a long way to go before achieving an impact on childhood cancer patient outcomes. Further progress in the diagnosis and treatment of childhood cancers will require multidisciplinary integrated healthcare and research data platforms that enable real-world data simulations of machine-learning algorithms and AI in data-driven clinical decision support applications for the benefit of patients. The novel technologies of AI and Big Data can advance potentially life-saving research and use of information efficiently to underpin long-term follow-up care as well as to understand the causes of childhood cancer. We must ensure that Europe's children and youngest citizens affected by cancer can fully partake, and benefit from the emerging AI, Big Data and machine-learning technologies.”

Thus, the strong commitment at the policy level and the supportive vision of the pediatric cancer community in Europe suggest a European cancer policy landscape that is keen to maximise the use of AI in the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of childhood cancer.

Although the concept of artificial intelligence (AI) was born decades ago [1], the increased availability of computational power at affordable cost represents a significant push in its application to several domains. Yet, AI in medicine is underdeveloped, although the perspectives of its application are wide and very promising [2]. The several applications of AI in cancer are

intuitive, as they may fully support the digital health care of these patients through patient data management including the integration of next generation sequencing, analysis of imaging and pathology, and may accelerate drug discovery [3]. These components represent the foundation of precision oncology which aims at precisely targeting and characterizing individual tumor cells. AI algorithms require large amounts of data to be accurately trained. The availability of appropriate datasets and their interoperability represent essential requirements for a widespread application of AI in medicine [4]. However, the numerous data sources currently used in clinical studies are often fragmented and not accessible to third parties. Moreover, the application of AI in clinical activities raises some ethical concerns [5]. As elaboration processes of AI are opaque and can be autonomous, it is challenging to understand the balance between autonomy and human supervision. Ethical challenges in AI are particularly important as they must be applied to children with a potential lethal disease. Finally, there is a likely convergence between telehealth and artificial intelligence that may powerfully interact with each other to digitally support the clinical patient journey [6].

This report illustrates the state of the art and the current developments of AI applications in pediatric cancer through a bibliometric review of the existing scientific publications and reviews, of existing clinical trials and other studies, of available data repositories, and through a discussion of the gaps and potential advancements in the field.

2.1. Bibliometric analysis

A bibliometric analysis is used to describe the general trends of scientific publications based on metadata annotated in the references, and on the number of citations and its correlated indexes. This approach is also useful to reveal the most frequent collaboration networks, the most popular scientific journals, and the most frequent topics of the available scientific literature in a certain domain based on authors' keywords. We performed a bibliometric analysis of the available scientific literature on AI and pediatric cancer from 2000 to 2021.

The first part of this analysis was conducted with no geographic restrictions to describe the trends on a global scale.

The scientific production regarding AI and pediatric cancer has been modest until 2015, when a rapid increase has been observed with an almost tenfold increase in the number of publications in 2020 compared with 2014 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of articles on AI and pediatric cancer published from January 2000 to June 2021.

This trend corresponds to the increasing availability of computational resources and the popularity of AI solutions in other healthcare domains, although the total volume of scientific publications in pediatric oncology is low.

The geographic area of origin of scientific papers included in this review is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Number of scientific publications AI and pediatric cancer by geographic area of origin (SCP: Single country publications; MCP: Multiple country publications).

Not only did European countries have a larger scientific production than other geographic areas, but they also had the largest proportion of scientific papers written in collaboration with authors from other countries compared with China and USA. Europe, China and the USA accounted for the majority of papers in this field.

When analyzing international collaborations between different countries based on the affiliation of authors (Figure 3), it is evident that strong connections exist between authors from the USA and China. European countries, however, show a dense collaboration network with each other, which is in line with the European research strategies in cancer. Other apparent collaboration networks exist between Portugal and Brazil and other Asian countries, and between Argentina and Denmark.

Figure 3. Country collaboration networks based on authors' affiliation. The most evident cluster is between the USA and China and other Asian and English speaking countries (red cluster). A dense collaboration network is evident among European countries (blue cluster). Additional collaboration networks include Portugal and Brazil and other Mediterranean and Eastern countries (green cluster) and between Argentina and Denmark (purple cluster).

Most of the scientific publications in the field of AI and pediatric cancer are available in journals that are not specific for oncology such as Scientific Reports and PLoS One (Table 1). Of note, most papers published before 2015 are in generic scientific journals or about medical imaging. This observation also explains a higher score in citation indexes in generic and informatics scientific journals.

Sources	n. articles	h_index	g_index	m_index	TC	NP	PY_start
SCIENTIFIC REPORTS	87	22	32	2,750	1246	70	2014
PLOS ONE	68	23	40	1,769	1787	63	2009
FRONTIERS IN ONCOLOGY	62	7	9	2,333	146	34	2019

BMC BIOINFORMATICS	51	21	40	1,050	1693	47	2002
IEEE ACCESS	50	12	27	3,000	800	43	2018
EUROPEAN RADIOLOGY	48	17	30		973	44	N/A
CANCERS	45	5	7	1,667	100	26	2019
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF IMAGING SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGY	40	8	10		139	26	N/A
BIOINFORMATICS	37	22	36	1,048	2361	36	2001
JOURNAL OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING	31	14	25	1,273	641	31	2011
MULTIMEDIA TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS	31	5	9		93	16	N/A
MEDICAL PHYSICS	30	9	20	1,000	788	20	2013
COMPUTERS IN BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE	29	12	22	0,923	522	25	2009
AMERICAN JOURNAL OF NEURORADIOLOGY	26	13	21	0,619	796	21	2001
FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY	25	11	15	2,200	274	21	2017
COMPUTER METHODS AND PROGRAMS IN BIOMEDICINE	23	11	17	0,688	304	19	2006
BIOMEDICAL SIGNAL PROCESSING AND CONTROL	22	10	16	0,909	297	16	2011
FRONTIERS IN NEUROSCIENCE	22	8	14	2,000	200	15	2018
EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF RADIOLOGY	21	9	11	1,125	161	21	2014
JOURNAL OF MEDICAL IMAGING	20	7	13	1,000	184	15	2015

Table 1. Number of publications and citation indexes for the 20 most frequent scientific journals hosting papers in AI applied to pediatric cancer. H-index: The Hirsch index (H-index) is a journal's number of published articles (h), each of which has been cited in other papers at least h time(s). m-index: The m-index is defined as H/n , where H is the H-index and n is the number of years since the first published paper of the journal. The g-index is an improvement of H-index. TC: Total number of Citations. NP: Net Production. PY_start: starting year of the journal.

Based on authors' keywords reported in scientific papers, it is possible to describe the general themes covered in the available publications. In Figure 4, we performed a cluster analysis to discover the most important thematic areas in the scientific literature of this field. The most frequent cluster shows a high frequency of themes regarding the integration of different information such as image, gene expression and histopathology data. A second cluster refers to segmentation of medical images and classification of tumors. Other clusters refer to feature extraction from medical images and integration of -omics.

Figure 4. Conceptual map based on cluster analysis of authors' keywords. The different conceptual clusters identify several concepts: image classification and integration with other data for classification of tumors (red); feature extraction from diagnostic images (green); image segmentation (blue); integration of -omics (purple); medical image processing (orange).

To further explore the concepts from authors' keywords, we selected clinical terms only and created a word cloud (Figure 5). The most frequent clinical terms include different brain tumors

Figure 6. Number of scientific publications on AI and pediatric cancer by European country of origin (SCP: Single country publications; MCP: Multiple country publications).

To better explore the collaboration network in Europe, we analyzed the authors' affiliation in the subset of scientific publications from Europe (Figure 7). This analysis shows a strong link between the US and several European countries, especially with Germany. A second cluster is centered on the UK that has collaborations with New Zealand and Singapore. Weaker networks are between France and the Mediterranean of Asian countries, and between Portugal and Brazil.

Figure 7. Country collaboration networks based on authors' affiliation in Europe only. The most evident cluster is between the USA, Germany, several other European countries and Canada (red cluster). A second collaboration network is evident among the UK, China and other various countries (purple cluster). Additional collaboration networks include France and other Mediterranean and Eastern countries (green cluster) and Portugal and Brazil (blue cluster).

We manually extracted from each paper the clinical diagnosis in which the AI intervention was applied. Table 2 illustrates the results of this analysis. The majority of AI interventions studied in selected papers were on brain tumors and leukemia. However, the list of childhood tumors in these papers does not include many common diagnoses.

	n	%
Brain tumors	186	61.2%
Leukemia	55	18.1%
Other tumors	27	8.9%
Lymphoma	24	7.9%
Neuroblastoma	15	4.9%
Wilms Tumor	11	3.6%
Ewing Sarcoma	7	2.3%
Rhabdomyosarcoma	6	2.0%
Osteosarcoma	6	2.0%
Hemopoietic stem cell transplant	3	1.0%
Leiomyosarcoma	1	0.3%

Table 2. Clinical diagnoses of AI interventions from the 304 European papers using manual review. Papers may have multiple diagnoses.

We manually classified the scope of the AI intervention in each single paper to explore the domains in which AI has been studied in pediatric cancer (Table 3). By far, the most frequent AI interventions included in the papers under review were about classification and diagnosis of pediatric cancer. Much less frequently, the papers under review were in regard to AI for planning treatment. When cross matching clinical diagnoses and scope of AI interventions, the most frequent correspondences were for brain tumors classification, diagnosis and segmentation.

	n	%
Classification	109	35.9%
Diagnosis	80	26.3%
Prognosis	51	16.8%
Segmentation	47	15.5%
Treatment	20	6.3%
Quality of Life	1	0.3%
Other	3	1.0%

Table 3. Scope of AI interventions from the 304 papers from Europe from manual review. Papers may have multiple scopes.

We also investigated which data source was used to train the AI intervention in each of the papers under review (Table 4). The most frequent category of data is MRI as most AI interventions are focused on the support to classification and interpretation of medical images. Surprisingly, some data sources, as ultrasound images and data from metagenomics, are much less frequent in these reviewed papers. Multiple data sources were rarely combined in the European reviewed papers accounting for only 5% of the total publications. The most frequent combinations were different diagnostic images sources such as MRI, CT and PET.

	n	%
MRI	140	46.1%
Histopathology	37	12.2%
Blood	25	8.2%
Gene expression	24	7.9%
CT	19	6.3%
DNA microarrays	18	5.9%
mRNA	10	3.3%
PET	8	2.6%
Hyperspectral image	7	2.3%
DNA methylation	7	2.3%
Transcriptome	6	2.0%
Clinical data	5	1.6%
Genetics	7	2.3%
Proteome	2	0.7%
Molecular model	2	0.7%
Ultrasound	1	0.3%
Social media	1	0.3%
Spectroscopy	1	0.3%
Microbiome	1	0.3%
Literature annotation	1	0.3%

Table 4. Data sources from the papers on AI and pediatric cancer published in Europe. Papers may have multiple data sources.

Finally, we also explored in this data subset, how frequently the AI intervention was compared to human capacity in terms of concordance and accuracy. The total number of papers including such a comparison with a human counterpart was evident in 31/304 papers (10.2%).

2.2 Scoping review of existing reviews

We screened the existing published medical literature from 2015 to 2021 to identify the existing reviews on AI and pediatric cancer. The objective of this scoping review was to find the existing evidence regarding the current AI applications for childhood cancer.

Twelve reviews were identified. In accordance with the results of our bibliometric analysis, there was a dramatic increase in the number of papers in recent years: all reviews but two were published since 2019. Similarly to our bibliometric analysis, brain tumors were the most represented disease group as 8 out of 12 reviews focused on the use of AI in this setting. In addition, one review focused on leukemia, one on hematopoietic stem cell transplant, and two on several tumors. The most explored field was imaging, with several aims. While, as expected, the use of AI systems to optimize highly repetitive processes (such as image segmentation) was widely investigated, an emerging trend involved the use of radiomic features in predicting the histological and molecular classification of tumors, with the aim to reduce the invasiveness of the diagnostic process. In the wake of this purpose, several reviews shed light on the use of AI to decrease patient exposure to radiation or contrast agents. Other issues explored were evaluation of response to therapy and patient prognosis. The only available review on leukemia [7] focused on identifying new genes potentially involved in risk classification without reporting any evidence; whereas another paper on HSCT underscored that most studies are related to post-HSCT complications, with the limitation of small numbers of patients [8].

Reference	Field of application	Aims	Evidence from the review regarding impact of AI solution
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[9] Huang J, et al.	Brain tumor imaging	Diagnosis and segmentation of several brain tumors. Prediction of glioma progression. Patient positioning for external beam radiation therapy.	For tumor diagnosis mean accuracy of 0.86 (range 0.72–0.95); in 5 of 6 studies AI outperformed humans. For other tasks accuracy was comparable with clinical experts. No studies described use of the AI tool in routine clinical practice.
[10] Forghani R	Brain tumors	Prediction of tumor histology, and patient survival.	An increasingly large body of literature suggests that radiomic features are useful for characterization of brain tumors, including prediction of tumor histologic characteristics, certain molecular characteristics and patient survival.
[11] Sanvito F, et al.	Brain tumors	Image segmentation in brain tumors.	Models showing good performance are already available open access.
[8] Gupta V, et al.	Hemopoietic stem cell transplant	Predicting transplant complications, including deaths, and best dose regimen for cyclosporine to prevent GvHD. Selecting donors.	The evidence is not sufficiently robust to determine the optimal ML technique to use in the hemopoietic stem cell transplant setting.

[12] Daldrup-Link H.	Imaging	<p>Accelerating the acquisition time of MRI scans.</p> <p>Reducing the dose of gadolinium-based contrast agents for brain MRI scans.</p> <p>Detecting pulmonary nodules on chest CTs of pediatric patients. Texture analysis and classification of pediatric brain tumors. Assessing tumor therapy response. Predicting survival in children with cancer and improving long-term outcomes.</p>	Dedicated applications of AI algorithms for children with cancer are limited.
[13] Sotoudeh H, et al.	Management of glioma	<p>Predicting glioma grading. Predicting tumor genomics from imaging data.</p> <p>Segmenting tumor, edema and normal tissue before surgical operation. Analyzing images from hyperspectral imaging during surgery to differentiate neoplastic tissue from adjacent non-tumoral brain tissues. Predicting glioma outcomes</p>	<p>Grade prediction based on imaging features is feasible by AI algorithms.</p> <p>Prediction of tumor genomics from imaging data is feasible by application of AI algorithm radiomics, with accuracy above 80–90%.</p> <p>AI techniques can segment tumor, edema and normal tissue with at least moderate accuracy. Analysis of hyperspectral imaging by AI can differentiate neoplastic tissue with accuracy about 80%. The overall</p>

		from imaging and clinical data.	accuracy of machine learning methods to predict glioma outcomes from imaging and clinical data approaches 80%.
[14] Sarkiss CA, et al.	Neuro-oncology	Predicting the patient outcomes and image segmentation. Detecting glioma genetic mutations using ML. Predicting prognosis in patients with high-grade glioma. Identification of targeted therapy by identifying new transcription genes.	ML can predict patient outcomes, with a sensitivity range of 78%–98% and specificity range of 76%–95%. ML based algorithms show accuracy in diagnosing low-grade versus high-grade gliomas, ranging from 80% to 93% and 90% for diagnosing high-grade glioma versus lymphoma.
[15] Abdel Razek AAK, et al.	Neuro-oncology imaging	Extracting radiomic and radiogenomic features of posterior fossa tumors and other brain tumors.	Most research studies are deficient in validation of their generated models; this hampers the applicability of AI methods. The performance of each

			model is task-dependent and dataset-dependent.
[16] Ak M, et al.	Neuro-oncology imaging	<p>Differentiation of pediatric ependymoma and medulloblastoma. Predicting distinct medulloblastoma subgroups.</p> <p>Predicting BRAF status in pediatric low-grade gliomas before a biopsy.</p> <p>Radiomic application in natural killer cell infusion in children with recurrent medulloblastoma and ependymoma.</p>	AI can differentiate the types of pediatric posterior fossa tumors with fair accuracy.

[17] Azimi P, et al.	Neurosurgery	Use of artificial neural networks in supporting diagnosis: imaging for pediatric posterior fossa tumors and brain tumors; proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy for tumor and non-tumor cerebral disorders; differential diagnosis of epilepsy seizures and brain tumor through EEG. Use of artificial neural networks in predicting outcome: childhood hydrocephalus using endoscopic third ventriculostomy.	ANNs could assist radiologists in formulating optimal decisions for classifying brain tumors and are particularly suitable for analysis of complex cancer data.
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Table 5. Existing reviews on AI and pediatric cancer. Most papers focus on brain tumors and imaging. A summary of the evidence is provided: accelerating image acquisition, image segmentation, and extracting radiomic features to predict both diagnosis and prognosis are the most established uses of AI. Two reviews that did not report evidence were not included.

These areas of intervention could have a significant impact on clinical care. AI methods in image acquisition can save time and therefore resources in performing examinations. Notably, the reduced radiation exposure achieved in some studies represents a desirable goal in children who are particularly susceptible to radio-induced damages. The good performance achieved in image segmentation could save the clinician time to spend on finer, less repetitive activities. Also, the results achieved in the histological/molecular diagnosis of the tumor on imaging are quite satisfactory: *Huang et al.* in their review [9] found a mean accuracy of 0.86 (range 0.72–0.95), with AI outperforming the human counterpart in 5 of 6 studies: this could have an application in selected cases where invasive diagnostic procedures are too risky. Similarly, satisfactory accuracy was also found in predicting the prognosis of patients, with a sensitivity range of 78%–98% and specificity range of 76%–95% reported in the review by *Sarkiss et colleagues* [14].

Finally, it should be noted that some reviews offer an overview of the possible uses of AI without commenting on the evidence [18].

If the field of imaging is well studied, several gaps in the other fields inherent to pediatric oncology emerge from the analysis of the reviews: a large proportion of tumors are only marginally considered, as well as there is a lack of reviews regarding methods that can potentially benefit from the application of AI methods, such as the analysis of histological samples.

The reviews analyzed herein were published by 49 authors from 7 countries. Authors from the USA are the most represented (31 of 49 authors in 9 out of 12 publications). There are only 6 authors from EU countries and are included in only 3 reviews: German authors collaborate with authors from outside the EU in 2 of the reviews (one involved an author from Austria), while Italian authors exclusively wrote the other. This demonstrates how the EU has accumulated a delay in exploring the possible uses of AI in pediatric oncology compared with its transoceanic counterpart.

2.3 Existing studies registered on clinicaltrials.gov

We searched clinicaltrials.gov for studies conducted in the last 5 years (2016-2021) in which the intervention was based on AI and the study was enrolling children.

We obtained 61 entries and scanned the dataset in order to exclude clinical trials that included only malignant entities that are uncommon in children. A total of 26 entries were selected. Although patients younger than 18 years of age were formally eligible in these studies, only one trial (NCT04763109) was primarily designed for testing machine learning based algorithms in a population of pediatric patients with the objective of comparing a novel whole-body Magnetic Resonance Imaging with an AI intervention in children with neurofibromatosis Type 1. Table 6 describes the studies found on clinicaltrials.gov.

NCT Number	Title	AI intervention
NCT02991105	Epidemiology of Cancer After Solid Organ Transplantation - EpCOT Study	Risk stratification of solid organ transplant recipients at risk for cancer
NCT03452774	SYNERGY-AI: Artificial Intelligence Based Precision Oncology Clinical Trial Matching and Registry	Dynamic matching based on clinical trial allocation and availability for optimized matching

NCT03552497	The Potential of Radiomics to Differentiate Between Malignant and Benign Bosniak 3 Renal Cysts.	Differential diagnosis between malignant and benign Bosniak 3 renal cysts based on radiomics
NCT03750890	Visual Study of Molecular Genotype in Glioma Evolution	Identification of specific molecular markers in the progression of glioma and intrinsic connection of radiomics features and microomics molecular markers
NCT03798795	Radiomics for Tumor Grading of Soft Tissue Sarcomas.	Developing predictive radiomics model for tumor grading
NCT03857373	Renal Cancer Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks	Detecting renal tumors from CT urography scans
NCT03871140	Utility of Ultrasound Imaging for Diagnosis of Focal Liver Lesions: A Radiomics Analysis	Accurate segmentation, detection and classification of liver lesions on US images. Linking the liver cancer feature to optimal ablation parameters
NCT04022512	Accuracy of Deep-learning Algorithm for Detection and Risk Stratification of Lung Nodules	Detection and risk stratification of lung nodules in osteogenic sarcoma patients
NCT04215211	MR Based Survival Prediction of Glioma Patients Using Artificial Intelligence	Survival prediction for glioma patients
NCT04215224	Histopathology Images Based Survival Prediction of Glioma Patients Using Artificial Intelligence	Survival prediction for glioma patients
NCT04217018	MR Based Prediction of Molecular Pathology in Glioma Using Artificial Intelligence	Prediction of molecular pathology or subgroups of gliomas
NCT04217044	Histopathology Images Based Prediction of Molecular Pathology in Glioma Using Artificial Intelligence	Prediction of molecular pathology or subgroups of gliomas
NCT04220424	Glioma Patients Registry Based on Radiological, Histopathological and Genetic Analysis	Prediction of molecular pathology and clinical outcomes of glioma patients

NCT04249895	Comprehensive Digital Archive of Cancer Imaging-Radiation Oncology(CHAVI-RO)	Extraction of radiomic features
NCT04442425	Machine Learning to Analyze Facial Imaging, Voice and Spoken Language for the Capture and Classification of Cancer/Tumor Pain	Using facial and voice recognition technology to classify pain
NCT04469244	Evaluation of the Use of Radiomics in 18F-FDOPA PET Examinations for the Characterization of Gliomas	Predicting the molecular characteristics at initial diagnosis and response to glioma treatments
NCT04576416	Artificial Intelligence Augmented Training in Skin Cancer Diagnostics for General Practitioners	AI enhanced case training on a library of 10,000+ benign and malignant skin lesion
NCT04682886	Radiomics Analysis of Focal Liver Lesions Based on Contrast-Enhanced Ultrasound Imaging	Accurate segmentation, detection and classification of liver lesions
NCT04695015	Research of Pathological Imaging Diagnosis of Ocular Tumors Based on New Artificial Intelligence Algorithm	Establishing AI-assisted image data and diagnostic algorithm for eye tumors
NCT04758988	AI Augmented Training for Skin Specialists	AI augmented training on skin cancer
NCT04763109	Identification of Pre-Malignant Lesions In Pediatric Patients With Neurofibromatosis Type 1 Using Novel Magnetic Resonance Imaging Techniques Paired With Artificial Intelligence	Estimating the positive predictive value of changes in Magnetic Resonance Imaging scans from baseline to 12-months
NCT04952818	The Value of Preoperative Diagnosis and Prognostic Prediction Based on Radiomics of Giant Cell Tumor of Spine	Radiomic model for preoperative risk stratification for spinal Giant Cell Tumor of Spine
NCT05033678	Implementation of Teledermoscopy and Artificial Intelligence	Introducing AI within teledermoscopy
NCT05062772	Brain Tumor Intraoperative Ultrasound Database	Feature selection and extraction techniques for characteristics that have greater discriminating power.

		Elaborating a predictive model of survival
NCT05110430	Automated Detection of Metastatic Bone Disease on Bone Scintigraphy Scans	Improving clinical decision based on bone scintigraphy scans
NCT05112510	Prognostic Prediction of NPC Based on MR Diffusion-Weighted Imaging	Building a radiomics and a clinical model for nasopharyngeal carcinoma prognosis

Table 6. Registered clinical studies on clinicaltrials.gov exploring AI in cancer and enrolling children. A summary of AI intervention is provided.

Almost all studies focused on solid tumors, whereas malignant hematologic diseases, which account for most pediatric cancers, are rarely included. Central nervous system tumors seem to be the most attractive subject for AI research, particularly gliomas; on the other side, other brain neoplasms that are more common in children than adults (such as medulloblastomas or ependymomas) are not eligible in any registered trials. It is also noteworthy that a significant number of clinical trials concern skin cancers, often aiming to investigate the potential of portable devices in recognizing malignant lesions.

AI algorithms in these studies are often applied to diagnostics of tumors, especially by magnetic resonance imaging or computed tomography scanning, and for this reason CNS and other solid tumors got the lion's share of AI research. There is no doubt that radiomics represents the most interesting field of application, as only AI is able to analyze such a quantity of data as those generated by radiological diagnostics. In addition to radiomics, applications of AI include imaging-based models for survival prediction or risk stratification as well as detection on novel biomarkers from histopathological data.

Nevertheless, almost all studies that we have detected are observational, while only three have implemented machine learning algorithms into the decision-making process and have exploited AI in clinical activity.

Furthermore, only 8 studies involved at least one center located in a European country, which represents a small portion of the original dataset. Differently from the US and China, European studies seem more limited to single research groups lacking international cooperation.

The fragmentation of both research groups and the subject of these studies, limit the application of AI systems to a fraction of the entire horizon of pediatric cancers.

2.4 Data and repositories suitable for AI applications in pediatric cancer

As the majority of existing studies on AI and pediatric cancer are developed using data from single centers, pursuing the objective of data sharing to increase the volume of the observations and data diversity is crucial. To this end, several initiatives have been developed in the US [19] but few in Europe. To map the available resources suitable to develop AI applications for pediatric cancer, we first searched for European registries on pediatric cancer and other scientific publications citing data repositories for pediatric cancer. We also searched for data repositories listed in studies registered in ENCePP. Overall, this search resulted in 108 scientific publications and 3 additional resources in ENCePP, for a total of 111 information sources.

We then reviewed the information included in this dataset and extracted a list of unique registries or other data repositories relevant to pediatric cancer. This list included a total of 50 unique items; those focused on pediatric cancer are illustrated in Table 7.

Name	Type of tumor	Country
Childhood Cancer SubRegistry of Belarus	Childhood cancer	Belarus
Danish Childhood Cancer Registry	Childhood cancer	Denmark
PanCare Life	Childhood cancer	Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Slovenia, Switzerland, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, France and the Netherlands
Adult Life After Childhood Cancer in Scandinavia	Childhood cancer	Denmark, Norway, Iceland, Finland, and Sweden
Socioeconomic Consequences in Adult Life after Childhood Cancer in Scandinavia	Childhood cancer	Denmark, Sweden and Finland
Registre National des cancer des l'enfant	Childhood cancer	France
CWS-SoTiSaR	Soft tissue sarcoma and other soft tissue tumors	Germany

German Childhood Cancer Registry	Childhood cancer	Germany
Individualized Therapy For Relapsed Malignancies in Childhood	Childhood cancer	Germany
European Rhabdoid Registry	Rhabdoid tumors	Germany, Netherlands, Denmark, Portugal, and Ireland
Nationwide Registry of Childhood Hematological Malignancies and Solid Tumors	Childhood cancer	Greece
National Pediatric Cancer Registry of Hungary	Childhood cancer	Hungary
SIOP-Renal Tumor Study Group (SIOP-RTSG)	Renal tumors	International
Associazione Italiana Emato Oncologia Pediatrica	Childhood cancer	Italy
The European Cooperative Study Group for Pediatric Rare Tumors (EXPeRT)	Rare tumors	Italy, France, United Kingdom, Poland and Germany
Cancer Registry of Norway	Childhood cancer	Norway
Registro Español de Tumores Infantiles	Childhood cancer	Spain
Svenska Barncancerregistret	Childhood cancer	Sweden
Childhood Cancer Registry	Childhood cancer	Switzerland
SKION LATER Study	Childhood cancer	the Netherlands
SIOPE DIPG Registry	DIPG	the Netherlands, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Italy, France, the United Kingdom, and Croatia
Northern Region Young Persons' Malignant Disease Registry	Childhood cancer	UK
West Midlands Regional Children's Tumour Registry	Childhood cancer	UK

Table 7. Pediatric registries for cancer in Europe found through literature search.

The literature review also showed that information about childhood cancers was derived from registries that included adults in some studies. The list of repositories for all age groups used for extracting information on childhood cancer is reported in Table 8.

Name	Specific disease	Country
National Cancer Data Repository	Cancer	England
CancerData	Cancer	England
RENOCLIP-LOC Network (Rare cancers of the central nervous system)	Rare cancers of the central nervous system	France
FRANCIM France Cancer Registry	Cancer	France
Sarcoma Relapse Registry for Relapsed Sarcoma of Bone and Soft Tissues	Sarcoma	Germany
Hungarian Cancer Registry	Cancer	Hungary
Iceland Cancer Registry	Cancer	Iceland
ROR-SUL (South Regional Cancer Registry)	Cancer	Portugal
North Region Cancer Registry of Portugal	Cancer	Portugal
Central Serbia Cancer Registry	Cancer	Serbia
Cancer Registry of the Cantons of Zurich, Zug, Schaffhausen and Schwyz	Cancer	Switzerland
Netherlands Cancer Registry (NCR)	Cancer	the Netherlands
National Cancer Registration and Analysis Service	Cancer	UK
National Cancer Registry of Ukraine	Cancer	Ukraine

Table 8. Adult registries for cancer in Europe used for studying childhood cancer found through literature search.

Briefly, a constellation of registries with different structures exists in Europe. Although the list of registries in our work may not be exhaustive since it's mainly based on a literature search, most

European countries are represented. The registries found in this review include repositories for all age groups, for children only, and registries focused on specific tumors.

Most of the repositories found in this review do not reveal on their website any information regarding accessibility of their data. Some of these repositories are used for national epidemiologic analyses and offer static reports in an aggregated form to any visitor, or they offer a user interface for launching queries to obtain customized aggregated tables. Some of the registries declare that external entities may apply for data access to perform research under specific data transfer agreements and contracts. Data sharing agreements, however, may be a barrier to timely research as procedural inefficiencies, incomplete information, a lack of incentives and familiarity with academic practices, and unresponsiveness of faculty may hamper this type of action [19]. In some cases, the coordinators of data repositories offer to external entities the possibility to use synthetic data that mirror the statistical properties of real data.

Information about interoperability of the repositories included in this review is scanty. Most data sources do not display their database structure and coding of the variables. Some of the existing repositories may be linked with other data sources at the national level for epidemiological purposes, as it happens in England where NHS digital is responsible for data linkage. Other repositories have developed IT-infrastructures to standardize data exchange and make it semantically interoperable. This approach is followed by the Sarcoma Relapse Registry, which also relies on open technology standards to guarantee future expansion to other partners. We did not find any repository with APIs available for external links. Nonetheless, several publications in our review used multiple registries or other datasets (i.e. data from clinical trials) for achieving their objectives. As no details about procedures used for data management are reported in these publications, it would be desirable to collect more information on the possibility that networks of registries and data pooling on pediatric cancer are feasible. Indeed, data harmonization remains an issue when different repositories should be linked [19].

Information on ethical and legal principles regulating the repository management was barely found in this dataset. Privacy is a main concern for most of the repositories showing details on management principles, and several repositories explicitly declare that any research activity based on their data is subject to approval of an ethical committee. Some of the websites declare that the data management is compliant to GDPR, which however, should be a regulation universally applied to all data repositories in Europe. However, some national repositories point also to national laws as a reference for data management which superimpose to GDPR.

Several published articles on AI applications for pediatric cancer use open repositories that are often utilized for training the AI algorithms. We screened the publications analyzed in section 2.1 originating from Europe to extract information on the open repositories that were used. We found 13 out of 304 of them reporting a web link that allowed us to review the characteristics of each repository. These open data included MRI images, microscopic images of blood samples, cytometry data, spectroscopy and microarrays. Most of the data were about brain tumors and

acute lymphoblastic leukemia. In general, these datasets are specific and do not include a large number of observations.

Open data is quite popular among researchers engaged in AI. Indeed, several open repositories exist that allow downloading datasets that can be reused in the development of algorithms. Some of the most popular resources in this domain, often located outside Europe, are reported in Table 9.

Name	Type of data	Population
Genomic Data Commons Data Portal	Genomic data	All ages
Kids first data resource center	Datasets from studies in different domains	Children
St. Jude Cloud Genomics Platform	Genomic data in tumors	Children
European genome-phenome archive	Genetic and phenotypic data	All ages
Catalogue of somatic mutations in cancer	Somatic mutations in cancer	All ages
PedcBioPortal for Childhood Cancer Genomics	Genomic data in tumors	Children
Pediatric Genomic Data Inventory	Genomic data in tumors	Children
Gene Expression Omnibus	Genomic data	All ages
GTEX portal	Gene expression data	All ages
Human Proteome Map	Proteomic data	All ages
Cancer imaging archive	Cancer imaging	All ages
Methylation in human cancer	DNA methylation	All ages

Table 9. Selected open platforms used in artificial intelligence research on cancer. Resources for supporting the upload and management of data exist for some of these platforms. For cBioPortal, a resource that allows the maintenance of mutations' data and clinical data, including patient and sample information, as well as timeline data is available for free (10.1186/s12911-021-01719-z).

As the number of these open repositories is low, there is some redundancy in their use within several scientific papers, highlighting a potential problem in ensuring data diversity when developing novel AI applications.

2.5 Ethical challenges in AI applied to pediatric cancer

The specific domain of AI and pediatric cancer has additional characteristics to common ethical issues in the application of AI to healthcare. First, cancer is a severe disease with a high impact on the quality of life of patients and families, sometimes leading to death. Secondly, focusing on pediatric patients has important implications since children are a fragile population and the entire family is involved in children's care. On one hand, AI has the potential to significantly improve the diagnostic, treatment and management processes of childhood cancer, but on the other hand, it is necessary to consider all the ethical implications of implementing AI in healthcare by design in this special population. A summary of the issues in the development of AI applications in the main peculiarities of pediatric cancer is illustrated below.

AI for children's health

The very nature of pediatrics and hence of pediatric oncology, is that the health communication process regarding the clinical management poses a greater impact in the entire family compared with adult patients. When dealing with AI, this can be particularly challenging. Explainability of AI has therefore important implications in this respect, especially for the informed consent in clinical studies or medical procedures supported by this technology. Finally, AI in pediatrics requires algorithms to be trained with data specifically obtained for this age group.

Cancers in children are rare diseases

The relative rarity of oncologic conditions in children requires a careful balance between the risk of re-identification from health data and benefits associated with the access to AI resources. This also suggests that, because of the scarcity of cases, clinical studies developing AI should be continuously fed with updated data. Furthermore, as AI should be based on big data, solutions for linking, pooling or federating data sources should be pursued.

Cancer is a severe, chronic and potentially lethal disease

This observation has important implications regarding the potential of errors which is inherent to the accuracy of AI applications. Undoubtedly, accuracy of AI tools in pediatric oncology should be as high as possible leaving small margins of error.

Timely diagnosis is often essential to increase success of therapy

Timely access to efficacious AI solutions should be granted as soon as possible. The complexity in developing AI solutions especially when developing multicentre initiatives may delay their availability and the opacity of AI processes may delay clinical decisions.

Genetic data are very important for cancer management

It is difficult to combine ethical principles for precision medicine and AI-communication issues. This observation calls for specific informed consent options. Genetic and genomic data also carry implications regarding data privacy and access to representative databases.

The European Commission presented a new proposal for an EU regulatory framework on AI in April 2021 [20]. The Commission proposes to establish a classification for AI systems with different requirements and obligations adapted to a "risk-based approach". The models of AI potentially developable in the field of pediatric oncology are intrinsically characterized by at least one of the elements that the EU has identified as "high risk" (for example: biometric identification and categorization of natural persons, medical devices), and therefore, any application in this area should comply with a range of requirements in particular on risk management, testing, technical robustness, data training and data governance, transparency, human control and cyber security [21].

In 2019, the High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), set up by the European Commission, published Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence [22], containing a list of seven requirements to which any AI system that is developed or used must adhere to: Human Agency and Oversight; Technical Robustness and Safety; Privacy and Data Governance; Transparency; Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness; Societal and Environmental Well-being; Accountability.

Not only the European Commission but also the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) consider transparency a fundamental requirement for AI systems in the healthcare sector [23]. Transparency is defined as patency of the AI systems themselves, in terms of explainability, traceability and communication on the limits of the AI system.

Many publications exist that discuss the ethical challenges of AI implementation in healthcare. However, most of the available literature considers generic scenarios that may not be tailored to pediatric oncology. For the reasons illustrated above, there is a need to design specific AI solutions for cancer in childhood that apply ethical criteria in this population. At present, AI is not yet completely and widely implemented in pediatric oncology, and therefore, few data are available regarding the ethical issues that may arise in the real world. For this reason, we elaborated clinical vignettes that will likely occur when AI tools become pervasive in pediatric oncology, and we discuss their ethical implications.

Imagine a pediatric dermatologist is using a new app which utilizes pictures taken with dermoscopy to return the probability that the lesion is malignant. The app was developed by a

software company which is very careful about the intellectual property of the developed algorithms. A child was screened for cutaneous nevi and, while the dermatologist does not recognize suspected lesions, the app sends a warning for high probability of melanoma in one of these nevi.

An AI system based on interpretation of transcriptomics for classifying medulloblastoma and indicating a suitable treatment returns a result conflicting with the opinion of oncologists about treatment. The oncological team discusses a final decision challenged by the absence of an apparent justification for the AI recommendation.

Since AI systems, under certain conditions, may provide better results than humans, it can be challenging to accept their support when they conflict with human decisions. Explainability of AI models represents one of the most important challenges limiting the wide implementation of this technology. Indeed, the explanation of AI, even if fully achieved, does not warrant a good performance, which is rarely tested in comparison with human decision and is often limited to a description of the model rather than its justification [24].

Explainability can be considered as <<a characteristic of an AI-driven system allowing a person to reconstruct why a certain AI produced the presented predictions>>. The inherent explainability of traditional algorithms makes them transparent AI models, whereas in deep learning algorithms explainability is opaque, due to the complex mechanisms of the system itself. Most of these are not designed to be constrained to interpretability and are too complex to be understood by a human (formulating the “black box” problem). Black box machine learning models would unlikely be used for high-stakes medical decisions unless no interpretable model with the same level of accuracy can be constructed. [25]. As a consequence, lack of explainability may have important legal and ethical implications.

A software company has developed a new system that, based on the integration of diagnostic images plus laboratory and genetic information by AI, is able to define a new biomarker useful for tailoring treatment. The company sponsors a clinical trial for comparing this system with traditional tumor classification approaches. The principal investigator has to explain to participants in the clinical trial what the new system consists of.

A novel AI system that predicts the prognosis in children with lymphoma is being tested in a clinical trial center at a hospital. None of the investigators have a background in informatics and AI despite having to manage the informed consent process for trial participation.

The problem of providing the right information to patients and their families participating in clinical studies during the informed consent process is particularly acute for AI and pediatric cancer. First, it's not obvious that an AI model will perform better than a more traditional statistical model

(sometimes traditional model) such as logistic regression and may even be subject to bias, limiting its applicability [25]. Secondly, it would be hard for a medical doctor with traditional training to explain in detail how an AI system will work in such a scenario, challenging the informed consent process itself [26].

A group of web hackers linked different sources of anonymous health data of children with cancer diseases and re-identified them. The hackers used anonymous data from a clinical study made publicly available, and other nominal data, including educational records. The reconciled information is on sale on the dark web.

A ransomware attack is launched to a hospital. All the activities linked to electronic applications of the hospital cannot be continued, including all decision support systems based on AI and clinical data. Moreover, health data of patients, including children with cancer, may be sold online.

The potential for re-identification of anonymized data is a concrete risk which should be considered in the application of AI tools, even when using appropriate strategies for data protection [27]. However, the risk of breaking anonymity and privacy clashes with the perception of values of personal data from the general public [28]. In fact, most people do not worry about preserving their privacy when making decisions for their health. GDPR strongly supports the idea that patients can autonomously manage their personal data, especially when dealing with sensible information as in health management. However, it seems unlikely that patients and their families have the sufficient knowledge to evaluate risks and benefits of opening their personal data [29]. These risks seem to be on the rise especially with the increase of cyberattacks to health organizations and the low capacity of health institutions to prevent them.

A global challenge is launched to develop an algorithm for detecting and classifying the cardiotoxic effects of a cancer treatment in childhood. To develop such an algorithm, it is essential to share data from a high number of clinical sites. After the start of the programme, some European clinical sites originally enrolled declare they cannot participate as data for feeding the algorithm would be located in a server outside of the European Union.

A novel algorithm has been developed for a decision support system for interpretation of laboratory exams useful to detect acute lymphoblastic leukemia in children. The preliminary data are encouraging, but the algorithm on which the decision support system is based has been trained on data from two clinical centers only, and its accuracy in other centers does not exceed 70%. It is likely that the accuracy of the system may improve if more data will be used for training the algorithm.

One of the great challenges of implementing accurate AI applications is ensuring that a large amount of data originates from diverse sources. At present, GDPR [30] limits the operations for sensitive data sharing when they should be transferred outside Europe. Although this challenge can be overcome, the complexity of bureaucracy has the potential to delay and sometimes prevent scientific collaborations that may result in significant benefits for patients [31].

For 2 years, a hospital has relied on an AI system for automatic segmentation of brain MRI of children with suspected brain tumors. This AI system must be deactivated for updates but the company is not able to restore the updated system for one month due to an unexpected technical issue. Because of the AI system, the hospital decided to reduce the number of radiologists in charge of the clinical service. Moreover, clinical radiologists have to return to using the manual segmentation of diagnostic images, prolonging the length of procedures and slowing down the diagnostic process.

Deskilling is a risk of automation that may result in problems when adequate preventive strategies are not considered. The same problem has been found in other domains where periodic training of manual skills seems reasonable. A typical example is civil aviation where AI supports the majority of actions. Yet, pilots must undergo periodic sessions on simulators for refreshing manual abilities, especially for emergency situations.

A final observation regards the correct interpretation of GDPR recommendations and the role of ethical committees. A multidisciplinary approach is needed for ensuring that all the ethical dimensions of AI in the specific domain of pediatric oncology are taken into account. Ethical committees should develop specific strategies for ensuring the application of ethical principles by design when dealing with AI applications, including the integration of an AI expert in the committee.

The vast majority of available publications on AI in pediatric cancer do not address the ethical implications of using AI in this population. However, we can expect that some challenges will be encountered as AI becomes more easily available in healthcare and in pediatric oncology.

2.6 Telemedicine and AI

Telemedicine can be defined as “the use of electronic information and telecommunications technologies to support long-distance clinical health care, patient and professional health-related education, public health, and health administration” [32].

The versatility and flexibility of both AI and telemedicine give endless possibilities for development [33]. In the oncology field, the integration of these technologies can enable different potential

applications throughout the spectrum of care, including: cancer screening, evaluation of baseline performance status, patient management while receiving treatment, acute post-treatment follow-up [32].

Some examples of promising opportunities for pediatric oncology innovation emerging from the intersection of AI and Telemedicine are reported in Table 7 and discussed below. It's important to highlight how the approach in digital health should always be patient-centric. In fact, every technological solution has to be evaluated across the patient journey, performing an assessment of unmet needs of the patient and transforming those needs into opportunities [34].

	Example of existing application	Possible application in pediatric oncology
Real time analysis of speech and facial expressions to detect health and emotional status	Assessment of human emotion from speech based on the visual representations of sound clips [35] and facial expressions using CNNs [36]	Emotion analysis in young cancer patients during televisit
Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) to create a real time recap of anamnesis and AI algorithm to support differential diagnosis based on symptoms	Automatic speech recognition model that can extract and relate key clinical concepts from clinical conversations combined with decision support system [37]	Support during televisit with notification alert for symptoms suggestive of neoplasia
Telerehabilitation systems: computer vision and wearables to analyse movements and support physical rehabilitation	Full body tracking system using computer vision during at-home exercises for elderly patients [38]	Post-treatment physical rehabilitation with a game-based interactive approach, using AI to analyze movements and customize treatments
Automated conversational interactions (chatbots and virtual assistants) for asynchronous support	Use of a chatbot for the promotion of well-being among young people after cancer treatment [39]	Timely and reliable response to patients and family questions and delivery of positive psychology skills
At-home management of chronic patients integrating multimodal signals from wearables (tele-monitoring)	Telehealth and virtual health monitoring in cystic fibrosis [40]	Post-treatment follow up and palliative care for childhood cancer patients

Integration of patient reported outcome (PRO) with wearable data for a comprehensive evaluation of the patient response to treatment

Perioperative optimization in surgical oncology patients analyzing patient-generated health data with AI [41]

Evaluation of chemotherapy efficacy and impact on children life outside the hospital setting, creating new outcomes for clinical trial research

Table 10. Technologies integrating AI and telemedicine and potential application in pediatric oncology.

Speech emotion recognition aims to analyze and assess the human emotional status to complement medical data captured during telemedicine sessions [35]. In addition, the recognition of facial expressions patterns using CNN has been integrated in telemedicine systems [36]. The above-mentioned technologies might represent a useful tool to partially make up for the lack of direct physical interaction of the doctor with the patient during televisit. One of the evident challenges in the existing algorithms, however, is that they are currently trained on adult data only and it would be helpful to study their performance with children data.

Another promising technology is Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) that allows the collection of structured data from a conversation, near human levels of performance have been reported for several ASR engines [42]. ASR could possibly be combined with a decision support system, as the one developed by IBM researchers [37], that reasoning on an initial set of provided symptoms generates AI-powered personalized questions and identifies high risk conditions. The above described tool implemented in a routine televisit could be adapted to give to the clinical a notification alert for symptoms suggestive of neoplasia, useful to detect, above others, pediatric tumors.

In the field of telerehabilitation, there is an interesting example concerning Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL). In this case, 40 potential home-based physical activities were proposed to ALL patients in order to strengthen the muscle–bone complex and prevent future impairment. A kinesiologist remotely supervised exercises, through an online telerehabilitation platform [43]. Telerehabilitation can be enhanced by the integration of data generated from wearables and video recordings. These sources of data enable, through a deep learning approach, to automatically analyze movements and improve performance of at home exercises. After the exercises are performed the kinesiologist is able to go over automatically produced reports, in the form of a live graph with the important angles between the body parts [38]. Beyond ALL, telerehabilitation plays a role even in cognitive impairment as it happens in brain tumors, which might benefit from the integration with AI.

Chatbot technologies are progressively being used to support adult cancer survivors and sometimes a dedicated interface for clinicians to fine-tune the chatbot behaviors is provided [44]. Several studies have suggested that 20%-30% of young people treated for cancer report moderate-to-severe psychological distress lasting into adulthood, which is the reason the feasibility of delivering positive psychology skills via a chatbot (*Vivibot*) in young adults (18-39

aged) has been investigated by Greer et al. [39]. Except for the above-mentioned study, the use of chatbots in supporting young cancer patients and their families is still unexplored. Some unmet needs of children affected by cancer could be accomplished by chatbots, considering their capability of offering support at any time with reliable answers to patients and family questions. A major area of integration between AI and telemedicine is the one of wearable devices, connected and smart objects (wristbands, watches, glasses, clothes, etc.) that measure health parameters (pulse, blood pressure, glycaemia, ECG, etc.), collecting a huge amount of data that can feed deep learning algorithms. Virtual monitoring, using wearables and AI, can off-load some of the burden of health monitoring to computers, with the assistance and mentorship of medical professionals. There are existing applications of virtual monitoring also in children patients, for instance the ones affected by cystic fibrosis [40].

Within the past decade, there has been increasing interest in integrating wearable technology with cancer care, particularly given its ability to incorporate passive data collection and minimize patient burden. The continuous monitoring via wearable devices can definitely play a role as an early-warning indicator for adverse outcomes [32]. The opportunities offered by tele-monitoring are not limited to post-treatment follow up, also terminally ill young cancer patients could benefit from it. Palliative care services could be effectively delivered at-home with the support of wearables and AI.

Biometric data collected using wearables can be categorized as patient-generated health data (PGHD). PGHD also includes Patient Reported Outcomes (PRO), reports of the status of a patient's health condition that come directly from the patient, in the form of disease-related symptoms, side effects of treatment, and quality of life assessments. Patient-focused drug development has primarily taken the form of a collection of PROs as secondary outcomes in clinical trials. On the other hand, remote collection of biometric data has been limited in this context [45]. There has been an increasing application of machine learning to PGHD, because it offers the possibility to integrate and analyze multimodal signals opening the opportunity for a comprehensive evaluation of the patient response to treatment. Electronic patient reported outcome (ePRO) together with biometric data, properly analyzed with AI, offer deep insights of an oncology patient's life outside the hospital setting, creating different outcomes that can't be ignored in clinical trials.

In order to evaluate if there were existing papers on the integration of telemedicine and AI in pediatric cancer, we performed a search on PubMed using the key words "artificial intelligence" and "telemedicine" combined with a string frequently used in reviews in pediatric oncology and applying the filter for the last 5 years. Our search produced only 8 results, none of which can be considered pertinent. Studies on the integration of these innovative technologies are lacking in pediatric oncology; the hope is that the disruptive potential of AI and Telemedicine will meet expectations as well as prove their utility in this field [46-53].

3. Conclusions

AI has the potential to represent an efficient solution for many unmet needs in pediatric oncology. The work presented in this report shows numerous potential areas of development and improvement that can match these needs. Indeed, most available AI solutions for pediatric oncology are limited to brain cancer imaging. The most important challenge in the development of AI algorithms is creating large databases that are necessary for high AI accuracy.

- a. Cancer in children may result from genetic changes that are currently unknown, either linked to inherited genetic changes or exposure to diagnostic or therapeutic radiation [54]. In essence, identification of conditions that can predispose to cancer, or polymorphisms of different genes that, if associated with each other, can increase the risk of neoplasms, represent a priority in pediatric oncology. AI can help to identify high-risk populations and prescribe the most appropriate screening test for each individual [55].
- b. In terms of diagnostic strategies, minimally invasive diagnostic tools with a broadened spectrum should be developed integrating different biometric data [56]. Moreover, with the same approach, it would be helpful to identify early disease markers, both for diagnosis and disease relapse. Most AI applications in pediatric oncology have been developed for imaging. However, there is still the need to find novel imaging biomarkers for different types of tumors [18]. The efforts to use non-invasive strategies for disease classification are of utmost importance. Indeed, tumors require a histopathologic classification that can be obtained with a surgical approach only. Predicting the prognosis of a tumor from images may help to avoid surgical demolition in low progressing cancers.
- c. Through AI it is possible to better classify pediatric tumors and precisely tailor therapeutic approaches to the biology of the tumor and the genotype of the host [57]. Personalized therapies and prediction of the impact of genomic variations on the sensitivity of normal and tumor tissue to chemotherapy or radiation therapy are definitely attainable with AI.
- d. AI can also improve the understanding of tumor spread by comparing molecular/anatomical features of primary tumors and metastases or by comparing multiple metastases in the same person and explore genetic, molecular and physiological factors associated with spontaneous tumor regression.
- e. The development of new treatments and drug repurposing is also an important issue [58]. Interesting studies with initial evidence in this respect have recently been published [59]. More tolerable and safe treatments would significantly improve the quality of life in this population. Among novel treatments, the identification of new opportunities for

immunotherapy and the evaluation of combination therapies deserve attention. Moreover, there is a need to rapidly forecast intrinsic resistance and to monitor for the emergence of acquired resistance. Investigating complex pathways to identify combination therapies that minimize the likelihood of disease recurrence, and of genes associated with an increased sensitivity to certain medications or that expose a greater drug toxicity may also help.

- f. AI may improve the efficiency of rehabilitation programmes for patients with physical or cognitive impairment when associated with telemedicine and help expand the access to these resources even from remote areas.
- g. At a more general level, AI may help shorten the time consumed in repetitive tasks. One area of work is in diagnostic imaging where automatic tumor segmentation is a reasonably close objective. Additional opportunities of AI in pediatric oncology are in supporting and accelerating randomized clinical trials for novel therapies, and integrating data from wearable sensors, patient reported outcomes and data from electronic health records. Finally, AI can be used for optimizing the journey of patients with pediatric cancer, thus shortening the path to diagnosis and treatment through the simulation and modeling of different clinical processes.

To achieve these objectives, an acceleration of research efforts is required in the implementation of AI in pediatric oncology at all levels, understanding that AI for adult cancers cannot be automatically translated into applications for children with tumors. Most importantly, this effort cannot be pursued in limited geographic areas, but has to be developed at a global scale to take advantage of a collective scientific effort and the largest possible amount of data. The strong international research activities in this field that Europe has been conducting with other continents represent an excellent starting point in this respect. An effort to pursue the development of AI applications with high accuracy relies on the inclusion of data from every segment of the global population and should be supported by strategies that overcome geographic and political borders, including in this process non-EU countries (including UK) should facilitate data sharing across borders.

Regarding AI for diagnostic images, the most developed area of research that includes radiomics, still suffers from a low degree of reproducibility and repeatability due to the paucity of existing studies and the rarity of multicentric initiatives in this field [18]. Indeed, the majority of available AI studies show that algorithms are trained on data acquired at a single institution, thus limiting their generalizability. Data-sharing privacy concerns and several other barriers preventing data linkage and multicentric collaborations result in low inter- and intra-observer variability of AI algorithms and ultimately decrease their generalizability. In fact, AI models may overfit to their training data and may fail to generalize to data not included in their data sets [60]. Although regulation constraints exist that may limit international data sharing with extra-EU countries, AI algorithms should be developed using data at a global

scale as much as possible. A collaboration between researchers and EHR providers may result in important achievements such as the creation of large database consortia among users of the same EHR platforms. A strategic effort should also be done to facilitate and reinforce data sharing from randomized clinical trials in which data have unique characteristics and high quality [61].

Moreover, there is a need for augmenting data collection for algorithm training, including online data and those generated by wearable devices [62]. In fact, remote collection, integration and analysis of patient data through telemedicine in pediatric oncology, is completely unexplored and may represent a significant progress to create hybrid and more efficient patient journeys. Finally, ensuring external validation through comparison of AI algorithms with humans, remains essential.

Interoperability and data harmonization are essential prerequisites for overcoming the existing fragmentation of data. Moreover, algorithms based on deep learning have been shown to increase their accuracy with the quantity of data used in the training phase. It seems therefore mandatory and ethical to facilitate data sharing whenever a new algorithm is developed in this field. One of the potential approaches is creating centralized repositories with data minimization that may be used for multiple purposes. Not only are centralized repositories challenging to set up and data minimization restricts information available, but AI development with centralized repositories is generally conducted using batch processes, while ideally, accurate algorithms require a continuous update. Other strategies such as the use of edge computing for supporting a continuous data flow, and the use of federated and swarm learning that seem more acceptable by health institutions, should be explored to improve the current approach [63, 64]. A secondary option, already explored by some registries, is developing synthetic datasets that resemble original data that overcome privacy concerns, maintaining original data fidelity [65].

From the ethical point of view, the “black-box” nature of AI remains a barrier to the widespread use of AI algorithms, pointing towards investing more resources for the creation of more transparent models [66]. This also has important implications for acquiring patient consent for procedures that rely on this technology. Finally, cost-benefit studies or prospective studies to confirm that AI can improve patient outcomes are still rare.

AI tools are still distant from clinical routine practice. To achieve a real integration of AI in disease management, physicians should receive training in computer/data science, and data scientists should become familiar with the complexity of clinical patient management. Secondly, integration of AI tools into a hospital’s EHR and PACS should be pursued [18]. Lastly, hospitals should adapt their IT infrastructures and computational resources to AI applications.

Finally, we must not forget that the ultimate intent of AI is assisting and augmenting physicians’ performance rather than competing with humans, and that the success of AI will

depend on human collaborations rather than on technical facilities. In this respect, beyond scientific networks, we should enhance the active role of patients, their families, and any associations of the patients that should contribute to a rapid implementation of AI taking into account patients' needs and ethical barriers and concerns.

4. References

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5. Appendix: Online search strategies

Search strategies for finding *data used in the bibliometric analysis*

Search string used in Web of Science for extracting bibliometric data on a global scale:

String	Concept
TS= (("artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning"))	General definitions of AI
TS= (("support vector machine" OR "random forest" OR "Markov decision process" OR "hidden Markov model" OR "fuzzy logic" OR "k-nearest neighbor" OR "naive Bayes" OR "Bayesian learning"))	Popular ML algorithms
TS=(("artificial neural network" OR "convolutional neural network" OR "recurrent neural network" OR "generative adversarial network" OR "deep belief network" OR "perceptron"))	Popular DL algorithms
(("natural language processing" OR "natural language understanding"))	NLP
TS=radiomic*	Radiomics
#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5	

<p>TS=((leukemia OR leukemi* OR leukaemi* OR "childhood ALL" OR AML OR lymphoma OR lymphom* OR hodgkin OR hodgkin* OR T-cell OR B-cell OR non-hodgkin OR sarcoma OR sarcom* OR sarcoma, Ewing's OR Ewing* OR osteosarcoma OR osteosarcom* OR wilms tumor OR wilms* OR nephroblastom* OR neuroblastoma OR neuroblastom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma OR rhabdomyosarcom* OR teratoma OR teratom* OR hepatoma OR hepatom* OR hepatoblastoma OR hepatoblastom* OR PNET OR medulloblastoma OR medulloblastom* OR PNET* OR "neuroectodermal tumor" OR retinoblastoma OR retinoblastom* OR meningioma OR meningiom* OR glioma OR gliom* OR "pediatric oncology" OR "paediatric oncology" OR "childhood cancer" OR "childhood tumor" OR "childhood tumors" OR "braintumor*" OR "brain tumour*" OR "brain neoplasms" OR "central nervous system neoplasm" OR "central nervous system neoplasms" OR "central nervous system tumor*" OR "central nervous system tumour*" OR "brain cancer*" OR "brain neoplasm*" OR "intracranial neoplasm*"))</p>		<p>Methods used in reviews for selecting childhood cancers</p>
#6 AND #7		
2000-2021		
Articles only		
English only		

We used a second dataset restricting the data to those belonging to European countries only, using filters available on Web of Science including 974 records. These records were manually

reviewed to select those applicable to children, resulting in 304 records. We then manually reviewed these records and added information about the type of cancer used in the publication, the scope of the work, the data source used for the AI application, and if the performance of the AI algorithm was compared with a human being. The Biblioshiny platform was used for the analysis of data (Aria, M. & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). Bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), pp 959-975, Elsevier, DOI: 10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007)

Search strategy for finding reviews

To search for published reviews on AI applications in pediatric cancer, we combined a search on PubMed with generic terms of AI and the string used by the Cochrane collaboration for childhood cancers. We then manually selected the reviews based on consistency of the publications. The analysis of reviews was limited to the last 5 years, from 2016 to 2021. We added a review published in 2014 as we believed it was relevant to our work.

Search strategy for finding existing studies on clinicaltrials.gov

We searched for studies registered on clinicaltrials.gov in the last 5 years, running the generic query “artificial intelligence” and then selecting the studies enrolling children only.

Search strategy for finding repositories on pediatric cancer

We started our review from a published review (Major A, Cox SM, Volchenboum SL. Using big data in pediatric oncology: Current applications and future directions. *Semin Oncol*. 2020 Feb;47(1):56-64. doi: 10.1053/j.seminoncol.2020.02.006. Epub 2020 Feb 29. PMID: 32229032.) and expanded it, including more recent publications using the same criteria. We also considered information from other publications (Gout AM, Arunachalam S, Finkelstein DB, Zhang J. Data-driven approaches to advance research and clinical care for pediatric cancer. *Biochim Biophys Acta Rev Cancer*. 2021 Aug;1876(1):188571. doi: 10.1016/j.bbcan.2021.188571. Epub 2021 May 26. PMID: 34051287.). Finally, we manually searched for repositories cited in the papers selected for the bibliometric analysis.

Search strategy for finding publications on telemedicine and AI

We launched the following query on PubMed:

"Artificial Intelligence" [Mesh] AND "Telemedicine"[Mesh] AND (leukemia OR leukemi* OR leukaemi* OR (childhood ALL) OR AML OR lymphoma OR lymphom* OR hodgkin OR hodgkin* OR T-cell OR B-cell OR non-hodgkin OR sarcoma OR sarcom* OR sarcoma, Ewing's OR Ewing* OR osteosarcoma OR osteosarcom* OR wilms tumor OR wilms* OR neuroblastom* OR neuroblastoma OR neuroblastom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma OR rhabdomyosarcom* OR teratoma OR teratom* OR hepatoma OR hepatom* OR hepatoblastoma OR hepatoblastom* OR PNET OR medulloblastoma OR medulloblastom* OR PNET* OR neuroectodermal tumors, primitive OR retinoblastoma OR retinoblastom* OR meningioma OR meningiom* OR glioma OR gliom* OR

pediatric oncology OR paediatric oncology OR childhood cancer OR childhood tumor OR childhood tumors OR brain tumor* OR brain tumour* OR brain neoplasms OR central nervous system neoplasm OR central nervous system neoplasms OR central nervous system tumor* OR central nervous system tumour* OR brain cancer* OR brain neoplasm* OR intracranial neoplasm* OR leukemia lymphocytic acute OR leukemia, lymphocytic, acute[mh]) Filters: in the last 5 years

